

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Tan**FIRST NAME:** Teck**PROGRAM CODE:** DBIO**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord for MAC (Microsoft 365)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. There is a risk of plagiarism when you do not credit the author of the source of information. You would need a citation for:

- A short sentence that has been paraphrased from a book.¹
- A well-known fact that people know instinctively.
- An anecdotal experience from your past.
- A historical date of a significant event that was found on the internet.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 37.

2. Constructs in a *qualitative study* are measured using tools such as observations, interviews, questionnaires and focus groups. What types of evidence can be documented to mitigate potential biases?
- Transparency, coherence and reliability.
 - Transparency, validity and reliability.
 - Transparency, coherence and credibility.**²
 - Validity and reliability.
3. In designing qualitative research, one must choose the right approach based on the philosophical assumptions and paradigms. Which one of these answers is NOT a commonly acceptable approach?
- The Narrative Approach.
 - The Phenomenological Approach.
 - The Grounded Theory Approach.
 - The Ethical Composition Approach.**³
4. Kate Turabian wrote, "... you must cite the sources of the facts, ideas, or words you use in your paper". Which of these is NOT a reason for citation?
- To guard against the charge of plagiarism, strengthen your argument and assist others who want to build on your work.

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Florida State University, 2017), 39–44.

³ Adu Philip, Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study, (YouTube, 2016), 12:14 min., <https://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.

- To give credit. When you cite the work of others, you provide them with the recognition they have earned.
 - To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts. Fellow researchers and readers need the source of the facts to check and judge their reliability, if required.
 - To pass the research ethics committee's scrutiny, because when things do not go your way, the method may be called into question.**⁴
5. In writing your dissertation, you may NOT include these optional components:
- Abstract of the study.
 - Dedication and/or Acknowledgement sections.**⁵
 - Table of Contents and lists of Tables and Figures.
 - Supervisory Committee page.
6. The dissertation concept paper and prospectus differ from the dissertation in some respects. Choose the *incorrect* statement:
- This is due to revisions to the introduction (chapter 1) and literature review (chapter 2) after recommendations by the doctoral supervisory committee.
 - The dissertation's methodology (chapter 3) changes from the future to the past tense.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139–40.

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 4.

- The abstract is first written in the concept paper and then revised for the prospectus and the dissertation.⁶**
- Findings (chapter 4) and discussion (chapter 5) are only found in the dissertation, not in the concept paper and prospectus.
7. Following a thorough and careful literature review, you have developed a *procedural schema* to answer the research questions for your qualitative study. What is the correct sequencing of these sections?
- Research questions → Participants → Sampling → Theory Implications → Policy Implications → Data Analysis → Hypothesis → Research Findings.
- Research questions → Design → Measures → Participants → Interviews → Data analysis → Limitations → Research Findings.
- Research questions → Research Design → Delimitations → Limitations → Data analysis → Discussion → Research Findings.
- Research questions → Research Design → Variables → Measures → Participants → Data analysis → Delimitations → Research Findings.⁷**
8. Which one represents a *Philosophical Assumption* paired with a specific *Paradigm* that helps inform qualitative research?
- Ontology (Nature of Reality) and Feminist Theory.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 3–7.

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 19.

- Epistemology (Co-creation of Knowledge) and Social Constructivism.**⁸
- Axiology (Role of Values) and Ethnography.
- Methodology (Process of Research) and Anthropology.
9. A good research argument consists of providing answers to some difficult questions. They may include the following, except:
- Claim: What do you want me to believe? What is your point?
- Plagiarism: Is this original work? Have you cited the sources?**⁹
- Reason: Why do you say that? Why should I agree?
- Evidence: What do you know? Can you back it up?
10. Chicago Style recommends capitalisation for books and articles, ethnic/racial groups, geographical names, and internet terminologies. Which one of these sentences is incorrectly capitalised?
- The University Of Chicago Press has just announced a recent Update to its system.**¹⁰
- I have visited countries in the northern regions of South America, but they were not as hot and humid as equatorial Singapore.
- Black Americans, compared with the Hispanic population in America, are twice as likely to be incarcerated.

⁸ Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, 7.19 min.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 57.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 45.

- The World Wide Web, also known as “the Web”, is easily accessible via smartphones and PCs.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

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